

Syntactic stylistic devices

Oyxunboeva Dilafruz Mahmud qizi

4 rd year students at Djizzakh branch of The National University of Uzbekistan
named after Mirzo Ulugbek

Supervisor: **Abduraxmanova Zilola Yoqubjon qizi**

Assistant teacher in the department Foreign Languages at Djizzakh branch of The
National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek

Annotation

This article gives information about Syntactic stylistic devices. In this article it has several paragraphs, which give full data about this. It is based on what is syntactic stylistic devices. In short, syntactic stylistic devices include inversion, indivisible structures, parallel devices, chiasm, repetition, ellipse, accent, counting, gradation, antithesis, and each of them performs a specific function. What is indivisible structures? What is the difference between chiasm and repetition? What is ellipse? In this article, candidates can learn how to be a good learner and what is stylistic devices and how to use it.

Key words:What is syntactic stylistic devices, inversion, indivisible structures, parallel devices, chiasm, repetition, ellipse, accent, counting, gradation, antithesis.

Syntactical stylistic devices

Syntactical stylistic devices are based on the syntactical arrangement of the elements of a sentences or a paragraph.

Besides there is a comparatively large group of syntactical stylistic devices in which the stylistic effect is achieved not only through a peculiar syntactical structure of the utterance, but also through the employment of the semantical side of its elements. To these we can refer repetition, climax, antithesis and represented speech. To finish up with the syntactical stylistic devices we shall describe the types of connection used stylistically: cumulation, asyndeton and polysyndeton.

Inversion

The violation of the traditional word order of the sentence (subject-predicate-object-adverbial

modifiers) which does not alter the meaning of the sentence only giving it an additional emotional coloring is called stylistic inversion.

Stylistic inversion may be of various types:

- 1) the predicate may precede the subject of the sentence;
- 2) the object is placed before the predicate;
- 3) the attribute stands after the word it modifies (the post-position of an attribute).

Stylistic inversion is used to single out some parts of the sentence and sometimes to heighten the emotional tension.

Ellipsis

The deliberate omission of one or more words in the sentence for definite stylistic purpose is called the stylistic device of ellipsis. The omission of some parts of the sentence is an ordinary and typical feature of the oral type of speech. In belle-letters style the peculiarities of the structure of the oral type of speech are partially reflected in the speech of characters (for example, the informal and careless character of speech). Some parts of the sentence may be omitted due to the excitement of the speaker. The stylistic device of ellipsis is sometimes used in the author's narration but more frequently it is used in represented speech. The stylistic device of ellipsis is sometimes used in the author's narration but more frequently it is used in represented speech. It is difficult to draw a line of demarcation between elliptical sentences and one-member sentences.

Parallelism is the repetition of grammatical elements in a piece of writing to create a harmonious effect. Sometimes, it involves repeating the exact same words, such as in the common phrases "easy come, easy go" and "veni, vidi, vici" ("I came, I saw, I conquered"). Chiasmus

Definition: reversal or crossing of grammatical structures in successive phrases or clauses. Example: " You forget what you want to remember, and you remember what you want to forget."

What is repetition in stylistics?

Repetition is a literary device that involves using the same word or phrase over and over again in a piece of writing or speech. Writers of all kinds use repetition, but it is particularly popular in oration and spoken word, where a listener's attention might be more limited.

Common Examples of Repetition

Time after time;

Heart-to-heart;

Hand in hand;

Get ready, get set, go;

REFERENCES

1. Abduraxmanova Z., & Mamurova, M. (2021). THEORETICAL APPROACH TO SPEECH DISFLUENCIES IN SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETATION. In *МОЛОДОЙ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬ: ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ* (pp. 43-45).
2. Ma'ripov J. K. A BRIEF INFORMATION ABOUT TENSES //O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY VA O'RTA. – С. 464.
3. Ma'ripov J. ANTROPOSENTRIZM–TILSHUNOSLIKNING ZAMONAVIY YONALISHI SIFATIDA //Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 28. – С. 62-68.
4. Rakhmatullayevna, A. D. (2021). The role and translation of metaphors in poetry. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF DISCOURSE ON INNOVATION, INTEGRATION AND EDUCATION*, 2(2), 332-335.
5. Rakhmatullayevna, A. D. (2022). TEACHING WAYS OF IDIOMS IN CLASS. *PEDAGOG*, 1(3), 370-373.
6. Raxmatullayevna, A. D. (2022). KOMMUNIKATIV KOMPETESIYANI SHAKLLANTIRUVCHI TARJIMA USULLARI. 68
7. 1. Nasiba, P. (2022). THE IMPORTANCE OF TASK-BASED LEARNING IN DEVELOPING SPEAKING SKILLS. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(11), 793-797.
8. Rachel Mitchell's book "IELTS reading strategies: the ultimate guide with tips and tricks on how to get a target band score on 8 in 10 minutes a day"